

THE ROLE AND IMPORTANCE OF GEOMETRIC PATTERNS IN THE ARCHITECTURE OF HISTORICAL MONUMENTS

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ABSTRACT

Of particular importance in this article is the fact that geometric patterns from the unique examples of our architecture are carefully taught to future generations and young professionals in terms of the artistic structure of the school of woodcarving, pottery and other carvings. In the further development of the Samarkand school of wood carving, our youth has the fineness of carvings, the complexity of the pattern, the vegetative entrance; and the use of floral girth patterns and the need to carefully study the coloring of the carved surface.

Unique monuments reflecting the heritage of Islamic civilization play an important role in the architecture of Uzbekistan, in particular in Samarkand, Bukhara, Khiva, Tashkent, Kesh, Nasaf, Termez, Andijan, Margilan and Kokand, various historical monuments and modern residential and public buildings.

Our compatriots, who visited the historical and cultural monuments of Uzbekistan, do not hide their admiration and admiration for the image of geometric ornaments and patterns, which are skillfully displayed by many foreign tourists.

Decorating buildings with geometric patterns has long enriched the human

spiritual worldview. Therefore, in architecture, special attention is paid to the decoration of buildings. If we look at the unique architectural monuments that have come down to us, we see that the geometric patterns in the art of decorating them are constantly improving.

In the minarets of mosques built in Bukhara in the XVIII-XVIII-XIX centuries, geometric patterns were used with flat roofs, single-story, carved ceilings. The walls were divided into arches and the altar was decorated. The top of the altar is decorated with mesh, carved chains and kundal patterns.

Geometric patterns are widely used in Khorezm architectural monuments, and the columns are decorated with elegant

patterns from the rich creative potential of folk carving.

One of the types of geometric patterns is girix, which means tangled, knot. Geometric pattern is a type of complex pattern, one of the types of geometric patterns, which consists of triangles, circles and arcs, as well as polygons. The geometric pattern consists of continuous reports, each report having its own structure. Painting terms Ruta is a two-way pattern distribution, i.e. a border pattern. Its size is often around 14-20 cm. Hoshiya patterns are different, depending on the design of the altar, the room, there will be lula khoshiya, ishkomb and other types. Munabbat - in Arabic means ustirmok. A pattern distribution that consists of a square or rectangle at the base and is repeated in four directions. It is used in the decoration of large surfaces. Munabbat has plant-like, geometric and other compositional types. He has the terms munabbati mehrob, munabbati bofta, munabbati islimi, munabbati girix and others.

attached to any pattern, and its shape has been developed and enriched over the centuries.

Manifestation in architecture - Persian view, landscape. The representation is an independent composition that does not connect to anything, and belongs to the type of complex geometric patterns. It has vegetative, geometric, floral girth, symbolic and other types. The representations will have a symmetrical and asymmetrical structure.

Also, as a continuation of the above ideas, geometric pattern plays an important role in the art of carving as an important integral joint. If we look at the history of the art of carving;

In architecture, orange is a type of pattern that is drawn to the center of the composition in geometric patterns. In geometric patterns, orange is a composition that hangs without being

One of the most common types of Uzbek folk decorative arts is carving. Engraving is the process of carving or embossing geometric patterns on metal art objects. In the territory of Uzbekistan, the production of metal art is an ancient art, which is second only to ceramics in its antiquity. There has been a great demand for carvings in trade since ancient times. Local works of art have been enriched with the best achievements of art from neighboring countries. Local craftsmen

made various items from gold, silver, copper, copper and other metals. Ancient

and early medieval carving is mainly reflected in the silverware.

From the 11th century, carvings began to be made from copper and copper alloys. Archaeological finds indicate that the first (special copper alloy) pins were widespread in Egypt, the Mediterranean, Mesopotamia, India, and Central Asia in the late 3rd and early 2nd centuries BC. These artistic metal objects were the first examples of workmanship. The pins depict small events, animals, and other things. A ceremonial cauldron found in Fergana proved that an "animal style" had been developed in carving in the middle of the 1st millennium.

The names of foreign masters can be found in metal objects found in archeological excavations in the country. The reason for this was that Timur moved foreign masters to Samarkand during his marches.

After the independence of the Republic of Uzbekistan, as in many areas, a lot of positive work has been done in the field of restoration and development of folk crafts.

As we mentioned at the beginning of our topic, the art of wood carving is also

one of the most ancient types of applied art, geometric wood carving pattern.

Archaeological excavations at the bottom of the Round Hill in the Surkhandarya oasis have proved that this type of art was well developed in these areas one and a half thousand years ago.

A number of cities in Central Asia, such as Bukhara, Samarkand, Urgench, Balkh and Mavr, were overthrown by the Mongol invaders led by Genghis Khan. In the second half of the 14th century, Jahongir Amir Temur put an end to these destructions by uniting the peoples of Central Asia and contributed to the development of culture and art of our people, including wood carving, with his monuments and relics.

He gathered in Samarkand great artists, poets, scholars, craftsmen and built many mosques, madrasas, khanaqas, palaces and other large structures. After the death of Amir Temur, due to the clashes between the Timurids, it had a negative impact on the development of culture.

In the 16th century, the appearance of architectural structures was further improved, many public buildings,

caravanserais, bridge cisterns, bathhouses, timber and other stalls were built in the cities. The history and appearance of the

monumental buildings were changed, artel artisans were formed. The mosques were built in the style of palaces, the mosques in the guzars and mahallas were built in

winter and summer, the large porches were decorated with carved columns and the doors were decorated with carved ornaments.

By the seventh century, feudal strife and wars in Central Asia were raging, and the Iranian invasion of Khiva and others had a negative impact on architecture and art. Artists and craftsmen were forced to go to India, to the Baburi palace. By the end of the 18th century, architecture and applied

decorative arts began to develop. In the construction of the palace, using the methods of composition of folk architecture, the construction of interior buildings, swimming pools, multi-column awnings, sinched buildings began.

The school of wood carving is more important than other schools due to the smallness of the carved patterns, the lack of ground, the density of the branches, the playfulness of the artistic structure, ie the spiral shape of the branches.

In the Samarkand school of wood carving, the smallness of the carvings, the complexity of the pattern, the vegetative entrance; and the floral girth is distinguished by the extensive use of patterns and the coloration of the carved surface.

The art of pottery is also remarkable and has a very ancient history. Pottery is one of the oldest forms of architectural and decorative art in Uzbekistan, and by the twentieth century its main centers were

Khiva, Bukhara, Tashkent, Samarkand, Andijan, Namangan, Kokand.

The art of pottery is more closely related to the art of architecture than to other types of folk applied and decorative art. Since ancient times, pottery has adorned palaces, mosques and madrassas, as well as the homes of wealthy townspeople. Initially, the construction had a strong connection to local school-specific traditions.

The technical process of Bukhara school pottery is quite complex, with unique styles of workmanship and colorful tones. The style of work of Samarkand masters is close to Bukhara plaster, and the upper corners of the walls are decorated with carved panels through the stalactite style of complex plaster. The most common

plant-Islamic compositions in the Tashkent school are close to the works of Fergana masters, and often form patterns in the category of "plant chains". The works of Kokand and Khiva potters are rich in intricate geometric patterns.

In the middle of the twentieth century, the tradition of pottery was on the verge of disappearance, but since the 1970s in Tashkent and other cities of Uzbekistan tried to effectively use pottery in the construction of objects of state importance, shops, cafes. Therefore, in the 1990s, a high-level school of pottery was developed in Tashkent, and their activities decorated the interiors of all historical buildings of the capital and the country. ("White Palace" residence, Oliy Majlis building, "Turkiston" concert hall, State Museum of Temurid History, "Navruz" wedding, capital theaters, metro stations, etc.).

At present, pottery is a mature form of applied and decorative art, which plays an important role in the decoration of architectural structures in Uzbekistan. The demand for creative samples of potters shows that they are international.

In conclusion, it should be noted that the decoration of buildings with geometric patterns has long enriched the spiritual worldview of man. Therefore, in architecture, special attention is paid to the

decoration of buildings. If we look at the unique architectural monuments that have come down to us, we see that the geometric patterns in the art of decorating them are constantly improving.

Geometric patterns are one of the types of applied art in Uzbekistan, which is able to amaze the peoples of the world with its great diversity and variety of colors. Every tourist who visits our country will definitely take home the samples of our wooden carvings made of various geometric patterns and make our art travel around the world.

Of particular interest in the unique examples of our architecture is the thorough training of future generations and young professionals in the art of geometric wood carving, the art of pottery and other carvings.

In the further development of the Samarkand school of wood carving, our young people have the fineness of carvings based on geometric patterns, the complexity of the pattern, the vegetative entrance; and the use of floral girth patterns and the coloring of the carved surface should be carefully studied. It is the duty of every citizen to pass on and preserve the architectural monuments of our ancestors to future generations.

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